

FUNCTIONAL PEARL

On greediness and inequality

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Abstract

How do we calculate programs? One approach, popularized recently by Bird (2010), starts with an inefficient reference implementation that is gradually transformed into an efficient algorithm. This approach runs aground when reasoning about functions that may return more than one correct solution: requiring the reference implementation and efficient algorithm to return exactly the same result is often too strong a requirement, especially when considering *greedy algorithms*. This pearl illustrates how calculating with specifications – using predicate transformers in the style of Dijkstra (1976) – provides a viable alternative to strictly equational techniques.

1 Introduction

In their book on *Algorithm Design with Haskell*, Bird and Gibbons (2020) give a careful treatment of greedy algorithms. Following their lead, we begin by considering the function that computes a *minimal cost candidate*, or *mcc* for short:

$$\begin{aligned}mcc &:: [Item] \rightarrow Candidate \\mcc &= minWith\ cost \circ candidates\end{aligned}$$

This function is defined in terms of two others: the first computes the list of all possible candidates; the second selects a candidate with minimal cost. Both of these functions are defined as a *fold* over lists. The *minWith* function finds an element with minimal cost in a non-empty list of candidate solutions:

$$\begin{aligned}minWith &:: Ord\ a \Rightarrow (Candidate \rightarrow a) \rightarrow [Candidate] \rightarrow Candidate \\minWith\ cost &= foldr1\ step\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}step &:: Candidate \rightarrow Candidate \rightarrow Candidate \\step\ x\ y &= \mathbf{if}\ cost\ x \leq cost\ y\ \mathbf{then}\ x\ \mathbf{else}\ y\end{aligned}$$

Note that if there is more than one element with minimal cost, the *minWith* function will return the *first* occurrence of this element. Replacing the comparison in the *step* function with a strict inequality would return the last occurrence instead. We do not fix the codomain of the *cost* function, requiring only that it maps to a total preorder.

Finding all possible candidate solutions starts from some initial candidate value c_0 . The *candidates* function repeatedly extends the current solution, adding a list of items one by one. The real work is done by the *add* function that is kept abstract; it extends a candidate solution, returning a (non-empty) new list of potential candidates.

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52 candidates :: [Item] → [Candidate]
53 candidates = foldr (concatMap ∘ add) [c0]
54   where
55     add :: Item → Candidate → [Candidate]
56

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57 Since the *candidates* function is defined using a fold, there is an obvious opportunity to apply
58 *fold fusion* to derive a more efficient solution. In general, the fusion law for lists states that for
59 given h, f, g and e the equality
60

$$61 \quad h (\text{foldr } f \ e \ xs) \quad = \quad \text{foldr } g \ (h \ e) \ xs$$

62 holds for all xs , provided the following fusion condition holds for all x and y :

$$63 \quad h (f \ x \ y) \quad = \quad g \ x \ (h \ y)$$

64 Using fold fusion, Bird and Gibbons show how to calculate a new function, *gmcc* that greedily
65 computes a minimal cost candidate and returns the same result as the *mcc* function above. To
66 apply fold fusion here, it suffices to find a function $gstep : Item \rightarrow Candidate \rightarrow Candidate$,
67 playing the role of h in the fusion formulas above. The *gstep* function must satisfy the
68 following equality for all items x and lists of candidates cs :
69

$$70 \quad \text{minWith } cost \ (\text{concatMap } (add \ x) \ cs) \quad = \quad gstep \ x \ (\text{minWith } cost \ cs)$$

71 In practice, this fusion condition, however, turns out to be ‘too strong in practice’ (Bird
72 and Rabe 2019). To address this ‘fly in the ointment,’ Bird and Rabe (2019) extend the
73 ambient functional language with a non-deterministic *MinWith* operator – but such language
74 extensions seem rather ad hoc. Is there no way to calculate a weaker greediness condition
75 directly? The rest of this pearl attempts to answers this question – but in doing so, no longer
76 reasons with *programs* but rather their *properties*. Where the equational reasoning used by
77 Bird shows how to derive an efficient program, the calculations here focus on identifying the
78 conditions necessary for these programs to be correct.
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83 2 Specifications and inequality

84 The heart of the problem lies in the choice of *specification*. Bird (2010) typically starts by
85 defining an inefficient function that is obviously correct. Fold fusion and equational reasoning
86 are used to uncover a more efficient implementation.
87

88 In the case of greedy algorithms, however, there may be more than one minimal cost
89 candidate. Using fold fusion to calculate a greedy algorithm guarantees both the greedy
90 algorithm and the *mcc* function produce *equal* results on all inputs. In particular, if there is
91 more than one candidate solution with minimal cost, both functions return the first one – but
92 there is no reason to favour one minimal cost candidate over the other! A better specification
93 leaves us with a bit more room to manoeuvre. We call a candidate *minimal* when its cost is
94 no greater than that of all other candidates. More formally, we define the following predicate:
95

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96 minimal :: Candidate → [Candidate] → Bool
97 minimal m cs = all (\c → cost m ≤ cost c) cs
98

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99 We write the specification of the *mcc* function, requiring that the cost of the candidate solution
100 m is no greater than any other candidate solution, as a (decidable) relation between its inputs
101 and outputs:
102

103 $spec :: [Item] \rightarrow Candidate \rightarrow Bool$
 104 $spec\ xs\ m = minimal\ m\ (candidates\ xs)$

105
 106 To be entirely precise, we should also require that m occurs in the list of all candidates. This
 107 property, however, is straightforward to establish and less relevant to the remainder of our
 108 calculations.

109 A greedy algorithm selects the ‘best’ choice of candidate at each step, rather than first
 110 generating all candidates and then selecting the minimal cost candidate.

111 $gmcc :: [Item] \rightarrow Candidate$
 112 $gmcc = foldr\ gstep\ c_0$
 113 **where**
 114 $gstep\ x\ c = minWith\ cost\ (add\ x\ c)$

117 Now this greedy algorithm may not produce a correct result – greedily selecting the best
 118 candidate in every step does not always lead to a globally best solution. With this definition
 119 in place, however, we calculate the required precondition for the greedy algorithm to return a
 120 minimal cost candidate.

121 What does it mean to calculate a precondition? Usually we associate predicate transformer
 122 semantics with imperative programs – but it is easy to forget that predicate transformers
 123 themselves are *functions*. In fact, the *weakest precondition* is simply (reversed) function
 124 composition:
 125

126 $wp :: (a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow (b \rightarrow Bool) \rightarrow (a \rightarrow Bool)$
 127 $wp\ f\ p = p \circ f$

129 Put differently, the weakest precondition that guarantees the postcondition p holds after
 130 executing f , trivially amounts to requiring that $p \circ f$ holds on input values.

131 In our example, however, we have defined the specification $spec$ as a *relation* between
 132 inputs and outputs. To handle such relational specifications, we need a slight generalization
 133 of the wp predicate transformer:
 134

135 $wp :: (a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow (a \rightarrow b \rightarrow Bool) \rightarrow (a \rightarrow Bool)$
 136 $wp\ f\ p = \lambda x \rightarrow (p\ x)\ (f\ x)$

138 Functional programmers may recognize the corresponding predicate transformer as the
 139 (flipped) S combinator.

140 So when *does* the greedy algorithm satisfy its specification? That is, when does the
 141 following condition hold on a list xs ?
 142

143 $wp\ gmcc\ spec\ xs$

144 When xs is empty, we observe that both the original mcc function and the greedy function $gmcc$
 145 function return the empty candidate c_0 ; the desired condition $wp\ gmcc\ spec\ []$ holds trivially.
 146 As we have assumed the $cost$ function maps to a preorder, it is necessarily reflexive—hence
 147 the desired inequality holds.
 148

149 The case for non-empty lists requires a bit more work. The derivation in Figure 1 calculates
 150 a sufficient precondition that ensures the greedy algorithm is correct. This derivation is given
 151 in the style of [Dijkstra \(1976\)](#), using the proof format attributed to Feijen (see [Van Gasteren](#)
 152 [1988](#), p. 107). We cover the three salient steps in more detail. Throughout the calculation,
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154   wp gmcc spec (x : xs)
155   ⇔ definition of wp
156   spec (x : xs) (gmcc (x : xs))
157   ⇔ definition of spec
158   minimal (gmcc (x : xs)) (candidates (x : xs))
159   ⇔ definition of candidates
160   minimal (gmcc (x : xs)) (concatMap (add x) (candidates xs))
161   ⇔ definition of candidates
162   minimal (gmcc (x : xs)) (concatMap (add x) (candidates xs))
163   ⇔ distributivity
164   all (λc → minimal (gmcc (x : xs)) (add x c)) (candidates xs)
165   ⇔ induction hypothesis
166   cost (gmcc xs) ≤ cost c ⇒ minimal (gmcc (x : xs)) (add x c)
167   ⇔ definitions of gstep and gmcc
168   cost (gmcc xs) ≤ cost c ⇒ minimal (minWith cost (add x (gmcc xs))) (add x c)
169   ⇔ generalize and rename
170   cost c1 ≤ cost c2 ⇒ minimal (minWith cost (add x c1)) (add x c2)
171   ⇔ minimality of minWith
172   cost c1 ≤ cost c2 ⇒ minWith cost (add x c1) ≤ minWith cost (add x c2)
173   ⇔ definition of gstep
174   cost c1 ≤ cost c2 ⇒ cost (gstep x c1) ≤ cost (gstep x c2)
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Fig. 1. Derivation of the greediness condition

we will (implicitly) universally quantify any free variables, just as is done in Haskell type signatures.

- Read from top to bottom, the first non-trivial step uses the distributivity property:

$$\text{minimal } m \text{ (concatMap } f \text{ cs)} \Leftrightarrow \text{all } (\lambda c \rightarrow \text{minimal } m \text{ (} f \text{ c)}) \text{ cs}$$

That is, a candidate is minimal for a list of the form *concatMap f cs* if and only if it is minimal for each individual list in the concatenation. This property was already proposed by [Bird and Rabe \(2019\)](#) and follows from a straightforward inductive argument.

- The use of the induction hypothesis is more interesting. Here we use the fact that for any predicates *p* and *q* we have:

$$(\forall x . p \ x \Rightarrow q \ x) \Rightarrow \text{all } p \ xs \Rightarrow \text{all } q \ xs$$

Recall that our induction hypothesis states:

$$\text{minimal (gmcc xs) (candidates xs)}$$

If we unfold the definition of *minimal*, this reads:

$$\text{all } (\lambda c \rightarrow \text{cost (gmcc xs)} \leq \text{cost } c) \text{ (candidates xs)}$$

This induction hypothesis plays the role of *all p xs* in the property above, after which the only statement left to verify is:

$$\forall c . \text{cost } (gmcc \text{ xs}) \leq \text{cost } c \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{minimal } (gmcc (x : \text{xs})) \text{ (add } x \text{ c)}$$

This step replaces the original property in terms of *all* with a single implication.

- The penultimate step uses transitivity of our preorder to establish that *m* is a lower bound of *cs*, provided *m* is less than the minimal element computed by the call *minWith cost cs*.

$$\text{cost } m \leq \text{cost } (\text{minWith cost cs}) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{minimal } m \text{ cs}$$

This last step of the calculation is the only part that relies on *minWith* in any meaningful way. In particular, the calculation never relies on the *definition* of *minWith*, but only uses the property that *minWith* returns a minimal element. Any alternative definition that returned, say the last minimal element in the list, would also suffice. This highlights the advantage of calculating with predicates, decoupling a function's implementation from its specification.

This completes the derivation of the necessary precondition for the greedy algorithm to produce the correct result, without using non-deterministic primitives such as *MinWith*. Bird and Rabe (2019) also consider using relation methods, as developed as part of the *Algebra of Programming* (Bird and de Moor 1996), but refrain from doing so as the solution is 'too drastic, more akin to a heart transplant than a tube of solvent for occasional use.' The point of this pearl is to demonstrate that lightweight relational methods, inspired by Dijkstra's work on predicate transformers, fit naturally in a functional setting. By working with the characteristic function of decidable relation, we manipulate functions in a familiar style, without the change of heart – abandoning functions in favour of relations – to which Bird and Rabe object. Simple calculational methods suffice, without resorting to further language extensions.

3 Greedy scheduling

With all the theory out of the way, an example is long overdue. Instead of redoing one of the examples by Bird and Gibbons, we tackle a scheduling problem whose greedy solution is not immediately obvious.

Suppose we have to schedule events in a conference room. Our aim is to schedule as many events as possible, but no two events may overlap. To keep things simple, we assume all events are equally important. Furthermore, each event is modeled by a pair of integers, representing the idealized start and end times:

newtype *Event* = *Event* { *start* :: *Int*, *finish* :: *Int* }

Two events are *disjoint* precisely when one of the two events ends before the other starts:

disjoint :: *Event* → *Event* → *Bool*

disjoint (*Event* (*s*₁, *f*₁)) (*Event* (*s*₂, *f*₂)) = *f*₁ ≤ *s*₂ ∨ *f*₂ ≤ *s*₁

To develop a bit of intuition, we visualize events as line segments that connect the start and end times:

To visualize many (potentially overlapping) events, we draw events at different positions on the y-axis. The vertical position of each line segment has no purpose, except to keep the visualization clean:

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A candidate solution is a list of events:

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type Candidate = [Event]
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A candidate solution is *valid* if each scheduled event is disjoint from all others:

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valid :: Candidate → Bool
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valid [] = True
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```
valid (e : es) = all (disjoint e) es ∧ valid es
```

The scheduling problem is to compute a longest valid candidate solution, given a list of all potential events. A brute force solution considers every possible subset of the input events, leading to an exponential algorithm. All the subsequences of our input list are readily computed:

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subseqs :: [a] → [[a]]
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subseqs [] = [[]]
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subseqs (x : xs) = map (x:) (subseqs xs) ++ subseqs xs
```

The brute force solution selects a valid subsequence with maximal length:

```
schedule :: [Event] → Candidate
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schedule = maxWith length ∘ filter valid ∘ subseqs
```

What about a greedy solution? Instead of computing all possible candidate solutions, the greedy algorithm keeps track of a single valid candidate, extending it with new events whenever possible:

```
greedy :: [Event] → Candidate
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greedy = foldr add []
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```
add :: Event → Candidate → Candidate
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add e es
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  | all (disjoint e) es = e : es
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  | otherwise           = es
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It is easy to check that the greedy algorithm always computes a valid solution. The more interesting question is: when does the greedy algorithm produce an optimal solution?

At first glance, it is not obvious that the greedy solution works at all. Greedily scheduling the earliest or latest events first will not produce an optimal solution. It is easy to find a counterexample:

Similarly, scheduling the shortest events first will not always produce an optimal solution:

What about scheduling events with the fewest conflicts first? After a bit of thought, you might find the following counterexample:

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To make matters worse, recall the *greediness condition* from the previous section fails to hold. Recall that the greediness condition (instantiated to this problem) reads:

$$\text{length } c_1 \leq \text{length } c_2 \Rightarrow \text{length } (\text{add } e \ c_1) \leq \text{length } (\text{add } e \ c_2)$$

It is worth understanding why this property does not hold. Suppose we aim to add the event labeled e to either one of the candidate solutions consisting solely of the events e_1 and e_2 respectively:

Even though $[e_1]$ and $[e_2]$ have equal length, the desired inequality fails to hold: we can add e to $[e_2]$ to produce a valid schedule, but not to $[e_1]$. This counterexample does, however, suggest a greedy strategy that might work: the key difference between e_1 and e_2 is that e_2 starts later than e_1 – does greedily scheduling the events with the latest start time first leads to an optimal solution? Calculamus!

The optimality property that the greedy algorithm should satisfy states:

$$\text{optimal} :: \text{Candidate} \rightarrow [\text{Event}] \rightarrow \text{Bool}$$

$$\text{optimal } m \text{ es} = \text{all } (\lambda c \rightarrow \text{valid } c \Rightarrow \text{length } c \leq \text{length } m) \ (\text{subseqs } \text{es})$$

There is, however, a problem with this definition. The specification is *too weak*: as we add new elements to our candidate solution, we have lost too much information about the start times of scheduled events. In the example above, we already saw that the two candidate solutions, $[e_1]$ and $[e_2]$, have the same length – but clearly one is preferable over the other. To address this, we need to replace the *cost* function introduced by Bird and Gibbons with a more general *relation*.

To warm up, we define the relation between events e_1 and e_2 characterizing when e_2 starts after e_1 :

$$\text{later} :: \text{Event} \rightarrow \text{Event} \rightarrow \text{Bool}$$

$$\text{later } e_1 \ e_2 = \text{start } e_1 \leq \text{start } e_2$$

To compare candidates, we take the pairwise lifting of this relation:

$$\text{pairwise} :: (a \rightarrow b \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \rightarrow [a] \rightarrow [b] \rightarrow \text{Bool}$$

$$\text{pairwise } p \ (x : xs) \ (y : ys) = p \ x \ y \wedge \text{pairwise } p \ xs \ ys$$

$$\text{pairwise } p \ [] \ [] = \text{True}$$

$$\text{pairwise } p \ _ \ _ = \text{False}$$

$$(\preceq) : \text{Candidate} \rightarrow \text{Candidate} \rightarrow \text{Bool}$$

$$c_1 \preceq c_2 = \text{pairwise later } c_1 \ c_2$$

Using these definitions, we might try redefining the optimality condition as follows:

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358
359 all (λc → valid c ⇒ c ≤ add e (greedy es)) (subseqs (e : es))
360   ⇔ definition of subseqs
361 all (λc → valid c ⇒ c ≤ add e (greedy es)) (map (e:) subseqs es + subseqs es)
362   ⇔ all distributes over concatenation
363 all (λc → valid c ⇒ c ≤ add e (greedy es)) (map (e:) (subseqs es))
364   ∧ all (λc → valid c ⇒ c ≤ add e (greedy es)) (subseqs es)
365   ⇐ induction hypothesis
366 all (λc → valid c ⇒ c ≤ add e (greedy es)) (map (e:) (subseqs es))
367   ⇔ fusing all and map
368 all (λc → valid (e : c) ⇒ e : c ≤ add e (greedy es)) (subseqs es)
369   ⇐ induction hypothesis
370 all (later e) es
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```

Fig. 2. Calculating the necessary precondition for our greedy algorithm

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378 optimal :: Candidate → [Candidate] → Bool
379 optimal m es = all (λc → valid c ⇒ c ≤ m) (subseqs es)
380

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This specification, however, is *too strong*. This specification requires *all* valid subsequences to have the same length as the optimal solution – which is clearly not the case! To address this, we need to generalize the relation between candidates further.

To compare candidates of different lengths, we redefine the relation used to compare candidate solutions:

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384 (≤) :: Candidate → Candidate → Bool
385 xs ≤ ys = any [pairwise later xs suffix | (prefix, suffix) ← split ys]
386
387 where
388 split as = zip (inits as) (tails as)
389
390

```

This relation holds whenever we can always partition *ys* into a prefix and suffix, where the events in the suffix have a pairwise later start than those in *xs*. Using this ordering, we arrive at the final version of our specification:

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394 optimal :: Candidate → [Candidate] → Bool
395 optimal m es = all (λc → valid c ⇒ c ≤ m) (subseqs es)
396

```

This specification has the Goldilocks property: it is *just right*. This optimality condition is strong enough to prove the desired statement, but overly restrictive. It is easy to show that $xs \leq ys$ implies that $\text{length } xs \leq \text{length } ys$; furthermore, this revised relation is general enough to compare lists of different lengths.

All that remains, is to establish that our greedy algorithm produces a optimal solution. The base case is easy to check. The key calculation necessary in the inductive case is shown in Figure 2; again, we study the key proof steps in greater detail.

The proof uses the induction hypothesis twice. Our induction hypothesis states:

409 $all (\lambda c \rightarrow valid\ c \Rightarrow c \preceq greedy\ es) (subseqs\ es)$

410 The first application of the induction hypothesis uses the following lemma

411 $xs \preceq ys \Rightarrow xs \preceq add\ e\ ys$

412 to establish that the greedy solution on the events $e : es$ is no worse than any solution that
413 draws its elements exclusively from es .

414 The second application of the induction hypothesis is more interesting. It relies on yet
415 another lemma that is not true in general:

416 $valid\ (e : ys) \wedge xs \preceq ys \Rightarrow (e : ys) \preceq add\ e\ xs$

417 Why does this property hold? When e is disjoint from xs , this property is obviously true.
418 When they conflict, however, there is more work to be done. From our hypothesis, $xs \preceq ys$, we
419 know that we can split ys into a prefix and suffix, where the events in suffix have a pairwise
420 later start than those in xs . We distinguish two last cases:

- 421 • If the prefix is non-empty, we can re-establish our invariant holds by moving its last
422 element to the suffix *provided e has a later start than all the elements in xs .*
- 423 • If the prefix is empty, we derive a contradiction. As adding e to xs failed, there must
424 be an element x in xs that conflicts with e . By our induction hypothesis, there is a
425 corresponding element y in ys with an earlier start than x . This element y must also
426 conflict with e , *when the events in xs and ys start later than e .* This contradicts our
427 assumption that the proposed solution $e : ys$ was a valid candidate solution.

428 This derivation establishes that the greedy solution produces an optimal result when the
429 event e starts later than all the elements of es ; for this hold at every position in our list of
430 input events, the list must be *sorted by increasing start times*. The very last step of the proof
431 is the crux: the greedy algorithm produces an optimal result when the input list is sorted.

432 A *linear algorithm*. When the input list is sorted, we can optimize the greedy algorithm even
433 further. In our current implementation, the *add* function checks if the next event is disjoint
434 from all other events that have been scheduled so far. Given that we are scheduling events in
435 order, it is far more efficient to only check if each new event conflicts with the *last scheduled*
436 event or not:

437 $add : Event \rightarrow Candidate \rightarrow Candidate$

438 $add\ x\ [] = [x]$

439 $add\ x\ es@(e : _)$

440 | $finish\ x \leq start\ e = x : es$

441 | *otherwise* = es

442 Given that this version of the *add* function takes constant time, the overall running time of
443 the algorithm is $O(n)$ on a sorted input list.

454 4 Discussion

455 This pearl aims to illustrate that it is worthwhile to have more than one tool in your calculational
456 toolbox. Fold fusion is fantastic tool to establish the *equality* of two functions – but is not
457 always useful when reasoning about non-deterministic functions, where more than one correct
458 solution may exist. More specifically, when reasoning about a specification given by an
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inequality, the style of calculation employed here seems a more natural fit. There is a trade-off here: rather than reason directly with programs, we reason about their specification given in a first-order predicate logic. Although the distinction between proofs and programs is blurred once one is used to programming with dependent types: the correctness proof of the greedy algorithm sketched here has a straightforward formalization.

It is no coincidence that we need the *any* and *all* predicate transformers, as these are the canonical predicate transformers associated with non-deterministic computations (Swierstra and Baanen 2019). Other non-deterministic operations proposed by Bird and Gibbons (2020), such as *ThinBy*, may also be written using these functions. Such thinnings are used when the *cost* function maps to a partial order, where not all candidate solutions are comparable. Rather than store a single best candidate, *thinning* algorithms maintain a list of possible candidates, pruning elements that are obviously redundant. The *thinBy xs ys* relation holds when *ys* is a subsequence of *xs* and every candidate in *xs* is superseded by one in *ys*:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{thinBy} &:: (a \rightarrow a \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \rightarrow [a] \rightarrow [a] \rightarrow \text{Bool} \\ \text{thinBy cmp xs ys} &= \text{all } (\lambda y \rightarrow y \in \text{xs}) \text{ ys} \\ &\wedge \text{all } (\lambda x \rightarrow \text{any } (\lambda y \rightarrow \text{cmp } y \ x) \text{ ys}) \text{ xs} \end{aligned}$$

Very little of this development depends on lists. Predicates and predicate transformers such as *any*, *all*, and *elem* can all be generalized to arbitrary traversable functors (Jaskielioff and O'Connor 2015; McBride and Paterson 2008). Indeed, the definitions of these functions in the Haskell base library work for any such traversable functor. Similar calculations may be readily performed on algorithms searching through inductive datatypes beyond lists.

References

- Richard Bird. 2010. *Pearls of Functional Algorithm Design*. Cambridge University Press.
- Richard Bird and Oege de Moor. 1996. *The Algebra of Programming*. Prentice-Hall.
- Richard Bird and Jeremy Gibbons. 2020. *Algorithm Design with Haskell*. Cambridge University Press.
- Richard Bird and Florian Rabe. 2019. How to calculate with nondeterministic functions. In *Mathematics of Program Construction: 13th International Conference, MPC 2019, Porto, Portugal, October 7–9, 2019, Proceedings 13*. Springer, 138–154.
- Edsger W. Dijkstra. 1976. *A discipline of programming*. Vol. 613924118. Prentice Hall.
- A.J.M. van Gasteren. 1988. *On the shape of mathematical arguments*. Ph.D. Dissertation. Department of Mathematics and Computer Science. <https://doi.org/10.6100/IR337809>
- Mauro Jaskielioff and Russell O'Connor. 2015. A representation theorem for second-order functionals. *Journal of Functional Programming* 25 (2015), e13. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0956796815000088>
- Conor McBride and Ross Paterson. 2008. Applicative programming with effects. *Journal of Functional Programming* 18, 1 (2008), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0956796807006326>
- Wouter Swierstra and Anne Baanen. 2019. A Predicate Transformer Semantics for Effects (Functional Pearl). *Proc. ACM Program. Lang.* 3, ICFP, Article 103 (jul 2019), 26 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3341707>

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